

Between knowledge and practice: A nationwide study of Indonesian household drug management

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Abstract

The ability to manage household medications influences the prevalent practice of self-medication in Indonesia. This study aims to evaluate the knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors (KAP) of the Indonesian population regarding household drug management. A cross-sectional survey involving 1,016 respondents was conducted across 31 provinces in Indonesia, utilizing a validated questionnaire. Most respondents were female (54.5%), within the age range of 26–35 years (44.4%), and possessed higher education (68.6%). The majority of respondents exhibited moderate levels of KAP regarding household drug management, with percentages of 58.5%, 96.7%, and 85.5%, respectively. Significant correlations were observed between income and levels of knowledge and attitude ($p < 0.05$), as well as between age and practice ($p < 0.05$). Moderate correlations were identified between knowledge and attitude ($r = 0.578$), knowledge and practice ($r = 0.485$), and attitude and practice ($r = 0.485$). These findings underscore the necessity for targeted, pharmacist-led educational interventions, particularly focusing on rational drug use, safe storage, and proper disposal practices.

Keywords

Attitude, behavior, drug management, knowledge, self-medication

Introduction

Self-medication is a global health phenomenon in which individuals diagnose and treat illnesses without consulting healthcare professionals (Aljinović-Vučić 2025). The World Health Organization recognizes it as part of responsible self-care while emphasizing that it requires appropriate knowledge and safe practices to prevent adverse outcomes (Limaye et al. 2017; World Health Organization 2025). Limited healthcare access, financial considerations,

and sociocultural beliefs drive self-medication in developing countries such as Indonesia (Coombs et al. 2022). Consequently, self-medication is not merely an individual behavior but a structural component of healthcare utilization that directly affects public health and system sustainability.

Indonesia faces distinctive challenges due to its population of over 270 million people distributed across thousands of islands, making self-medication a common primary healthcare strategy (Harapan et al. 2023; Roseno and Widyastiwi 2023). Approximately 80% of Indonesians

practice self-medication, and nearly half store medicines at home. However, inadequate household drug management increases the risk of irrational use, accidental poisoning, medicine wastage, and environmental contamination (Luo et al. 2021). Although the Ministry of Health has introduced initiatives such as the DAGUSIBU (Obtain, Use, Store, and Dispose of Medication) program and guidelines for proper storage and disposal, public awareness and implementation remain insufficient (Fathnin and Santoso 2023; Ridwanuloh 2023). A systematic review reported that 68.6% of respondents dispose of unused medicines in household garbage, reflecting persistent knowledge and practice gaps (Fathnin et al. 2025).

Household drug management is a multidimensional issue encompassing five interconnected practices: selection, purchasing, use, storage, and disposal (Luo et al. 2021). Mismanagement at any stage may generate clinical, social, economic, and environmental consequences, including treatment failure, antibiotic resistance, illegal resale of medicines, increased out-of-pocket expenditures, and ecological contamination (Maxwell 2016; Ayalew 2017; Locquet et al. 2017; Chung and Brooks 2019; Novias et al. 2022; Zheng et al. 2023; Sugihantoro et al. 2023). The Knowledge–Attitude–Practice (KAP) framework provides a theoretical basis for examining how knowledge shapes attitudes and ultimately influences behavior, enabling identification of gaps that can be targeted through policy and educational interventions (Andrade et al. 2020).

Despite growing evidence, nationwide data linking knowledge–practice gaps with medicine wastage, unsafe storage, and improper disposal in Indonesia remain extremely limited. Most prior studies are localized, use inconsistent KAP scoring thresholds, and do not generate nationally representative estimates capable of informing ministerial-level regulation or pharmacovigilance governance. Moreover, few studies explicitly quantify behavioral divergence between knowledge and practice using a unified analytical structure. Therefore, this study aims to quantitatively assess the national levels of knowledge and practice regarding household drug management in Indonesia, measure the magnitude of knowledge–practice gaps across the five management domains, and identify sociodemographic predictors of inappropriate practices, thereby providing methodologically validated and policy-relevant evidence to guide targeted interventions (Mustafa et al. 2023).

Materials and methods

Research design

This study employed a cross-sectional survey design to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of the Indonesian population regarding household drug management. The survey method was selected to estimate the prevalence and distribution of KAP levels and to examine associations between variables at a single point in time. Data were collected using a structured, self-administered

online questionnaire distributed nationwide to achieve broad geographic representation.

Study participants

A total of 1,016 adults aged 18–65 years from 31 provinces participated in the study. Participants were recruited through online dissemination using proportional quota sampling based on provincial populations to achieve diverse representation. Provincial quotas were calculated using the proportion of the adult population in each province according to the most recent national population data, and target sample sizes were allocated proportionally before recruitment began. The link to the online survey was shared on social media and community networks. The inclusion criteria included Indonesian citizenship, understanding Bahasa Indonesia, and willingness to provide informed consent. To reduce duplicate participation, the survey system restricted multiple submissions from the same device or account. Responses with incomplete KAP items were excluded using listwise deletion, and only fully completed questionnaires were included in the final analysis.

As the survey was conducted online and relied on self-reported responses, there is a possibility of information bias, including social desirability bias or inaccurate reporting of knowledge and practices. To mitigate this risk, the questionnaire was anonymous and devoid of personally identifiable information, and participants were apprised that there were no correct or incorrect responses. These measures were intended to encourage honest responses and minimize response distortion.

Research instrument

The questionnaire consisted of four sections: sociodemographic characteristics, knowledge (29 items), attitudes (25 items), and practices (27 items) related to medication selection, purchase, use, storage, and disposal.

- Reliability: Knowledge $\alpha = 0.805$; Attitude $\alpha = 0.617$; Practice $\alpha = 0.619$.
- Validity: Content validity index (CVI) was > 0.7 for all items; construct validity was confirmed with item–total correlations (*r*-value) above the minimum *r*-reference value of 0.062 (Suppl. material 1).

Thus, all questionnaires demonstrated good reliability and validity (Kline 1999; Suryadi et al. 2023). Knowledge items were measured using a Guttman (true/false) scale, while attitudes and practices were assessed using a 4-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 4 = strongly agree). Domain scores were summed and categorized into three levels. Cut-off points were determined using the minimum–maximum range method, in which the theoretical score range (maximum score minus minimum score) for each domain was divided into three equal intervals to generate proportionally equivalent categories (poor, moderate, high). Accordingly, scores were divided into:

- Knowledge: poor (0–9), moderate (10–19), and good (20–29);
- Attitude: poor (25–50), moderate (51–75), and good (76–100);
- Practice: poor (27–54), moderate (55–81), and good (82–108).

Collecting data

Data were collected via an online survey platform. Ethical approval was obtained from the Bioethics Commission of the Faculty of Medicine, Sultan Agung Islamic University (Ref: 136/IV/2024/Bioethics Commission).

Data analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic characteristics and KAP scores. Chi-square tests were employed to assess associations between demographic characteristics and KAP levels. Pearson correlation was used to examine relationships between KAP domains, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Sociodemographic characteristics of respondents

The respondents in this study were 1,016 participants from Indonesia, representing a diverse demographic distribution. The substantial number of participants across 31 of the 38 provinces in Indonesia demonstrates significant representativeness and involvement, making the sample suitable for further analysis in accordance with research standards (Table 1).

Table 1. Characteristics of respondents.

Characteristics	N	1016 (%)
Gender		
• Male	462	(45.5)
• Female	554	(54.5)
Age (years old)		
• 18–25	294	(28.9)
• 26–35	451	(44.4)
• 36–65	271	(26.7)
Education		
• Low (elementary, middle, and high school)	319	(31.4)
• High (bachelor's and master's)	697	(68.6)
Marital status		
• Married	564	(55.5)
• Unmarried	452	(44.5)
Employment status		
• Not/not working	210	(20.7)
• Entrepreneur	441	(43.4)
• Government employee	136	(13.4)
• Private employee	229	(22.5)
Income (IDR)		

Characteristics	N	1016 (%)
• < 3 million	256	(25.8)
• 3–5 million	516	(50.8)
• > 5 million	238	(23.4)
Number of family members		
• 1–2	168	(16.5)
• 3–4	677	(66.6)
• > 5	171	(16.8)
Medical history		
• Yes	384	(37.8)
• No	632	(62.2)
Type of disease (5 highest)		
• Hypertension	27	(7.1)
• Diabetes mellitus	20	(5.3)
• Cardiovascular Disease	19	-5
• Migraine	14	(3.7)
• Indigestion	13	(3.4)
Long-term treatment history		
• Yes	384	(37.8)
• No	632	(62.2)
Type of Medication (5 highest)		
• Antihistamines	160	-15.7
• Antidiabetics	92	-9
• Antibiotics	84	-8.3
• Analgesics	72	-7.1
• Decongestants	61	-6
Province of origin		
• Aceh	11	(0.9)
• Bali	18	(1.1)
• Banten	18	(1.1)
• Bengkulu	34	(3.0)
• DIY	15	(1.1)
• DKI Jakarta	15	(1.1)
• Jambi	30	(3.0)
• West Java	14	(1.0)
• Central Java	20	(2.0)
• East Java	24	(2.0)
• West Kalimantan	42	(4.0)
• South Kalimantan	38	(3.1)
• Central Kalimantan	41	(4.0)
• East Kalimantan	37	(3.1)
• North Kalimantan	36	(3.1)
• Bangka Belitung Islands	37	(3.1)
• Riau Islands	65	(6.0)
• Lampung	35	(3.0)
• Maluku	36	(3.1)
• North Maluku	32	(3.0)
• NTB	28	(2.1)
• NTT	30	(3.0)
• Papua	27	(2.1)
• West Papua	7	(0.7)
• South Sulawesi	37	(3.1)
• Sulawesi Central	31	(3.0)
• Southeast Sulawesi	25	(2.1)
• North Sulawesi	42	(4.0)
• West Sumatra	42	(4.0)
• South Sumatra	38	(3.1)
• North Sumatra	24	(2.0)

Demographic analysis revealed a predominance of females in the 26–35 years age group and a higher educational level. The majority of the individuals were married, with occupations as entrepreneurs, earning an income of 3–5 million rupiah (IDR), and had 3–4 family members. Most respondents had no medical history or long-term treatment history. The most frequently reported disease was hypertension, whereas the most commonly used medication was an antihistamine.

Knowledge, attitude, and practice categories

The majority of respondents possessed a moderate level of knowledge, attitude, and practice, as indicated by the category distribution in Fig. 1. Nonetheless, there was a tendency for perception to be the most moderate. Suppl. material 2 provides the distribution of respondents' answers for each item.

Figure 1. Categories distribution of knowledge, attitude, and practice (N = 1,016).

Relationship between characteristic and KAP categories

The relationship between characteristics was measured to determine factors related to the three levels of KAP variables. The chi-square test was chosen because the variables were ordinal data. This statistical analysis enabled a deeper understanding of how these characteristics impact knowledge, attitudes, and practices (Table 2).

The relationship between characteristics indicates that knowledge was significantly related to income and family size, attitude was only related to income, and practice was only linked to age. Additionally, there was no significant relationship between the three variables and other characteristics.

Correlation between knowledge, attitude, and practice

The correlation analysis among the three variables aimed to determine the linearity, strength, and type of relationship between them. The Pearson correlation test was employed because the data were numerical (Table 3).

The Pearson correlation analysis was performed to assess the relationship between knowledge, attitude, and practice scores among the respondents. The findings demonstrate that all three variables were positively, sig-

nificantly ($p < 0.05$), and moderately (above 0.40) correlated (Schober et al. 2018). These results suggest that as knowledge increases, both positive attitudes and better practices tend to follow.

Discussion

Sociodemographic characteristics

The sample consisted predominantly of females and individuals of productive age, reflecting common participation patterns in Indonesian health research and the national demographic structure (Atmi et al. 2024). Most respondents had higher education (diploma–doctoral level) and were employed in the private sector, consistent with Indonesia's economic profile (Atmi et al. 2024). A total of 37.8% reported a medical history, mainly hypertension and diabetes mellitus, aligning with the increasing burden of non-communicable diseases reported in the National Health Survey 2023 (Badan Kebijakan Pembangunan Kesehatan 2023). Overall, the distribution across provinces and sociodemographic groups supports reasonable national representation, while interpretation remains contextual (Ridwan et al. 2019).

Knowledge of household drug management

Only 38.1% of respondents demonstrated good knowledge, indicating persistent gaps in literacy related to managing household medications. This finding is consistent with a substantial body of evidence demonstrating that challenges related to health literacy remain pronounced in developing countries (Huang et al. 2019). Most of the people who answered the question (70.5%) knew that they should take their medicine according to the dosage on the packaging, and 62.9% knew that “three times daily” meant every eight hours. However, misconceptions persisted regarding bioequivalence between branded and generic medicines, classification of prescription versus over-the-counter drugs, interpretation of expiration and beyond-use dates, and management of missed doses (Isnenia and Julaiha 2024; Akhtar and Orayj 2024; Agustinus et al. 2025; Dhafin et al. 2025). Inadequate knowledge may lead to irrational drug use, including overdose, underdose, and other medication-related problems, which in turn contribute to antibiotic resistance and increased treatment costs (Melku et al. 2021). In contrast to earlier Indonesian studies indicating a limited comprehension of safe self-medication (Harapan et al. 2018; Sari et al. 2023). A relatively better understanding of disposal issues also supports the idea that environmental framing may help people get more involved in learning about medications (Mutmainah et al. 2022).

Attitudes and practices: consistency and gaps

Attitudes were predominantly moderate (96.7%), with no respondents categorized as poor, indicating generally favorable perceptions toward responsible drug management.

Table 2. Relationship between characteristics and KAP.

Characteristic	Knowledge (N)			Sig.	Attitude (N)			Sig.	Practice (N)		Sig.
	P	M	G		P	M	G		M	G	
Age (years old)											
18–25	8	169	117	0.817	2	288	4	0.454	253	41	0.048*
26–35	16	270	165		5	432	14		396	55	
36–65	11	155	105		1	262	8		220	51	
Gender											
Male	13	266	183	0.448	3	447	12	0.900	398	64	0.610
Female	22	328	204		5	535	14		471	83	
Education											
Low	7	186	126	0.308	3	309	7	0.826	268	51	0.352
High	28	408	261		5	673	19		601	96	
Marital status											
Unmarried	17	262	173	0.870	2	441	9	0.312	392	60	0.333
Married	18	332	214		6	541	17		477	87	
Employment status											
Not/ Not working yet	6	132	91	0.185	2	223	4	0.134	196	33	0.794
Entrepreneur	9	110	91		0	205	5		176	34	
Civil Servants	5	74	57		2	126	8		115	21	
Private employees	15	278	148		4	428	9		382	59	
Income											
< 3 million	8	137	117	0.010*	4	254	4	0.044*	214	48	0.076
4–5 million	9	160	80		1	244	4		215	34	
> 5 million	18	297	190		3	484	18		440	65	
Number of family members											
1–2	9	85	74	0.000*	1	162	5	0.662	140	28	0.538
3–4	20	408	249		6	658	13		587	90	
> 5	6	101	64		1	162	8		142	29	

*p value < 0.05; significance; KAP: knowledge, attitude, practice; G (good); M (moderate); P (poor).

Table 3. Pearson correlation test.

		Knowledge	Attitude	Practice
Knowledge	Pearson correlation	1	0.578	0.485
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000*	0.000*
Attitude	Pearson correlation	0.578	1	0.485
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000*		0.000*
Practice	Pearson correlation	0.485	0.485	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000*	0.000*	

*significance.

Positive attitudes help people accept public health interventions and give pharmacists more chances to teach, provide more pharmaceutical care, and offer telepharmacy services (Diepeveen et al. 2013; Pratiwi et al. 2020; Shafie et al. 2023; Sulistyaningrum et al. 2023). However, there were distinctions in attitudes and specific beliefs, including the notion that elevated prices correlate with superior quality, the assumption that regular refrigeration prolongs shelf life, and the acceptance of sharing prescription medications—practices that could compromise the stability and safety of drugs (Hajleh et al. 2021; Elghazaly et al. 2023). This generally positive attitude provides a strong foundation for developing effective educational and policy interventions, as favorable perceptions are key prerequisites for behavioral change and indicate that negative views toward responsible self-medication are not widespread in Indonesia (Wiryani and Karminingtyas 2022; Alves 2023). Practices were largely moderate (85.5%), with only 14.5% categorized as good. Similar to findings by Al-Qahtani et al. (2023), this indicates that awareness does not necessarily equate to optimal action. Risky behaviors encompassed neglecting to verify expiration

dates, improperly disposing of items, and discontinuing use due to side effects without seeking adequate guidance (Rahimah et al. 2022; Agrawal et al. 2023; Fathnin and Santoso 2023). This pattern illustrates the established knowledge–practice gap in health behavior research and emphasizes the necessity for comprehensive interventions that consider individual, social, and environmental factors affecting the shift from knowledge to action (Carrillo-González 2025).

Determinants and interrelationships of KAP

Chi-square analysis showed that age was significantly associated with practices ($p = 0.048$), suggesting behavioral variation across life stages (Talreja and Tiwari 2021). Furthermore, income was significantly associated with knowledge ($p = 0.010$) and attitudes ($p = 0.044$), supporting evidence that socioeconomic status influences access to health information and decision-making autonomy (Azmi et al. 2024). Family size was also associated with knowledge ($p = 0.000$) and attitudes ($p = 0.041$), highlighting the role of

intra-household information exchange and social support (Permatananda et al. 2020). Pearson correlation analysis demonstrated moderate positive correlations among knowledge, attitudes, and practices, consistent with behavioral theory that knowledge shapes attitudes and indirectly influences practice (Al-Zihra and Alkhalidi 2024; Lacs and Plaza 2025). However, the moderate strength of the association indicates that knowledge alone is insufficient to ensure optimal behavior, reinforcing the importance of structural, motivational, and environmental supports. Compared with prior localized studies, this nationwide evidence strengthens the understanding of the systemic knowledge–practice divergence in Indonesia and provides a clearer empirical basis for targeted policy and educational reform.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, although the study encompassed numerous provinces, many of the respondents possessed higher education. This could lead to sampling bias because people with more education and access to the internet are more likely to participate in online surveys. Consequently, the findings may indicate that individuals in these groups possess greater knowledge and engage in more responsible behaviors compared to those in rural, lower-literacy, or digitally underserved regions. Second, self-reported measures can still exhibit bias, even when anonymity safeguards are in place. Third, the cross-sectional design limits the ability to draw causal conclusions regarding the relationships among knowledge, attitudes, and practices.

Despite these constraints, this study represents the inaugural effort to provide a comprehensive national overview of household drug management through a standardized analytical framework. This serves as valuable baseline evidence for shaping policies and implementing targeted interventions, particularly aimed at enhancing outreach to vulnerable and low-literacy populations.

Conclusion

This research conducted throughout Indonesia indicates that adults generally demonstrate moderate levels of knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) related to household drug management. Despite the generally positive attitudes held by most individuals, the persistence of moderate practices indicates a moderate connection between knowledge and action. Significant associations were identified between KAP levels and age, income, and family size, indicating that sociodemographic factors influence how households manage their medications. These findings indicate a necessity for targeted educational initiatives led by pharmacists, emphasizing safe medication storage, wise drug utilization,

and appropriate disposal methods. Policy initiatives should focus on the enhancement of community pharmacy services, the expansion of digital and community-oriented health education programs, and the integration of structured campaigns for household medication management into national pharmaceutical governance strategies.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors declared that there are no conflicts of interest to disclose.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

The authors confirm their contributions to the paper as follows: study conception and design, FHF, S, ED, LL; data collection, FHF, ED; analysis and interpretation of results, S, DE; draft manuscript preparation, FHF, S, ED, LL. All authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Content Validity Index dan Construct Validity result

Authors: Fildza Huwaina Fathnin, Satibi, Dwi Endarti, Lutfan Lazuardi

Data type: docx

Explanation note: Contains the Content Validity Index (CVI) table and Construct Validity results (r value) supporting the rigor of the survey instrument.

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Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e183634.suppl1>

Supplementary material 2

Distribution of respondents' answers to questionnaire on Household Drug Management

Authors: Fildza Huwaina Fathnin, Satibi, Dwi Endarti, Lutfan Lazuardi

Data type: docx

Explanation note: Provides a table of the distribution of respondents' answers to the Household Drug Management questionnaire include KAP aspects, supporting transparency of national response patterns.

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